

ENVIRONMENTAL STRESS-CORROSION EDGE-CRACKING OF GLASS REINFORCED POLYESTERS

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ABSTRACT

The behaviour of cut coupons from carefully prepared $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ GRP laminates under the influence of a stress in the presence of aqueous acidic environments has been studied. A synergism between the applied stress and the corrodent on the formation and growth of transverse edge cracks is observed. Rapid crack initiation is more important than propagation since the longer cracks appear to grow more slowly by a diffusion controlled chemical attack. The major products of the corrosion are aluminium, calcium ions from the glass fibres, which develop spiral cracks in the ion depleted sheath.

Recently the phenomenon of strain corrosion cracking [1-4] in glass fibre reinforced composites has been reported. The stress relaxation process which takes place during these experiments makes results of time-to-failure tests under constant strain difficult to interpret. Thus tests under constant stress should lead to a better understanding of the phenomenon and to results which can be related more easily to the chemistry of failure. Bailey [5-9] and co-workers have studied in detail the behaviour of $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ cross-ply laminates in dynamic tensile tests and have reported theoretical models which predict the affects of laminate geometry on the transverse cracking behaviour. In particular, in epoxy/glass laminates, a knee in the stress-strain curve which corresponds to a visible whitening has been attributed to a reversible fibre-matrix debonding.

Thus the well characterised behaviour of transverse ply laminates caused us to use these specimen configurations in a study of the stress-corrosion behaviour of GRP in aqueous acidic environments. We anticipated that an overall change in the resin properties might lead to a reduction in the strain for the first transverse crack. The formation of these cracks does not involve specimen fracture and this type of damage is more convenient to study than time-to-failure experiments. However, our findings show that damage in the transverse ply is formed early on, in contact with aqueous solutions, and in the form of edge cracks growing slowly into the ply from both sides.

2.1 Laminate Preparation

We have chosen to study composites prepared from an isophthalic polyester resin (Scott-Bader Crystic 272), reinforced with Silenka E glass fibres of 1200 tex with a silane finish compatible with polyester and epoxy resins. The glass fibre was chosen because its handling characteristics makes it ideal for filament winding. A major application of filament wound pipes and containers is for transporting and storing aqueous solutions.

Laminates were made by winding individual plies of glass rovings carefully (initially by hand, more recently on a winding machine) onto metal frames. These are then laid up in the appropriate configuration before impregnation with resin. In order to maintain a relatively long working time and prevent excessive temperature build-up a relatively small quantity of accelerator was used. The curing system was 2% of a 50% methylethyl ketone peroxide solution (catalyst M) and 0.25% cobalt salt solution (Accelerator E) (Scott-Bader & Co. Ltd). Much difficulty has arisen with the formation of voids, inherent flaws and cracks. In particular, laminates post-cured for the recommended 3 hours at 80°C , after gelation at room temperature for 24 hours and made by a conventional procedure in which all three plies were wetted-out simultaneously, can be seen and heard to crack, on cooling from 80°C . The result is a laminate with excessive damage. Furthermore, when coupon specimens are cut from it, with a diamond saw, edge cracks can easily be formed.

We have found therefore that the best laminates with a $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ configuration are prepared by wetting out the inner ply, allowing it to gel for 24 hours under an applied pressure to achieve consistent volume fractions of glass, and subsequently laying up the outer plies on to it. In this way gelation stresses can be minimised and the noticeable dewetting during cure eliminated. The laminates are then gelled for a further 24 hours and then post-cured by heating at 50°C for 15 hours. The finish to the laminate is controlled by the use of melinex sheeting supported by glass plates. For surface analysis somewhat thicker melinex sheets ($175\mu\text{m}$) were used to achieve a perfectly smooth finish. The volume fractions of glass fibre

achieved were consistently $34 \pm 2\%$. Higher volume fractions of up to 45% have been achieved by this technique.

$0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminates have been made in the same manner but post-curing is accomplished off the frames, otherwise the thermal strains involved can lead to laminate fracture. The thermal strains produced in these laminates have been calculated from the radius of curvature of these unbalanced laminates, according to the method described previously [8]. Table 1 gives the values for the thermal strain developed in these laminates after cooling down from the post-cure temperature. Also included are the first transverse cracking strain (ϵ_{tlu}) and the deduced value of ϵ_{tu} ($\epsilon_{lt}^{th} + \epsilon_{tlu}$).

TABLE 1
Effect of Curing Conditions on the Properties of Cross-Ply
Glass Fibre Laminates from Crystic 272

Curing Schedule	Radius of Curvature of $0^\circ/90^\circ$ laminate	$\frac{\epsilon_{cl}^{th}}{\lambda}$	$\frac{\epsilon_{tlu}}{\lambda}$	$\frac{\epsilon_{cl}^{th} + \epsilon_{tlu}}{\lambda}$	$\frac{\epsilon_{lis}}{\lambda}$	$\frac{E_{c1}}{G_{lm} \cdot 2}$
170h at 18°C	> 100 *	0.0-0.12	0.59 ± 0.03	0.59	1.77 ± 0.1	16.0
+15h at 50°C	33 ± 2	0.33 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.03	0.57	0.84 ± 0.1	16.8
+3h at 80°C	27 ± 2	0.42 ± 0.03	0.17 ± 0.03	0.59	0.64 ± 0.1	17.5
+2h at 130°C	24 ± 1	0.52 ± 0.02	0.1 ± 0.02	0.61	0.66 ± 0.1	-

The measurements were all made on the same $0^\circ/90^\circ$ (ϵ_{lt}^{th} , or $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) laminate. Three specimens were used for each value. The laminate was allowed to fully cure at 18°C for 1 week before post-curing under the different conditions. ϵ_{cl}^{th} is the thermal strain in the transverse ply, ϵ_{tlu} is the transverse ply cracking strain, ϵ_{lis} (ϵ_{lt}^{th}) is the strain in the transverse ply, ϵ_{lis} is the applied strain for longitudinal splitting. E_{c1} is the Young Modulus of $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ laminate.

* The radius of curvature was rather temperature sensitive and samples could be seen to flatten out on changing temperature by 2° , the thermal strain is therefore taken as zero.

The latter value of ϵ_{tu} is seen to be a constant for the three curing conditions; this result is interesting since it shows that the transverse strength of an individual lamina is not affected by the various curing conditions.

Since it has been shown [8] by experiments on the straining stage in the electron microscope with $0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$ epoxy/glass laminates, that transverse failure originates from the coalescence of fibre debonds, we conclude that the different curing schedules do not affect the degree of bonding between the matrix and fibre. The resin properties however are improved on post-curing and this is seen in Table 1 by the increased values for the Young Modulus of the composite (E_{c1}). A knee was not observed in the stress-strain curve for these polyester laminates prior to the first transverse crack. This is in contrast to the epoxy systems where whitening associated with a knee in the stress-strain curve, is attributed to a reversible debonding phenomenon. The conclusion is that in these polyester laminates either all the fibres are

debonded, or that a series of debonds coalesce to form a transverse crack simultaneously. Since a change in modulus of the cold-cured specimen prior to transverse cracking is not observed and since the transverse cracks form more slowly than in epoxy systems, the latter seems more probable. Microstructural studies are underway and will be reported elsewhere.

The laminates were cut into specimens 15mm wide and 250mm long with a diamond saw. The inner ply was 1.25 ± 0.05 mm thick. Aluminium end-tags were stuck onto the specimens with an epoxy resin adhesive cured at 40°C or at room temperature for 48 hours. Two specimens were tensile tested to determine E_{cl} and ϵ_{tlu} and the appropriate applied stress, σ_a determined accordingly.

2.2 The Stress Corrosion Technique

The environmental tests have been carried out in a cell designed so that the specimen can be loaded in tension and that the half of the specimen outside of the environment could be used as a reference. Fig. 1 shows the experimental arrangement.

Fig. 1 The Corrosion Cell

The experiments were conducted in a creep machine and the applied stress (σ_a) was determined from the experimentally obtained laminate properties and was always such that the strain in the transverse ply was less than the transverse ply cracking strain ϵ_{tlu} . In this way any inherent stresses, in particular thermal stresses, were taken into account. The environment was contained initially in a quartz cell supported on the specimen with a cast silicone rubber seal. We have found that the analyses can be conducted in pyrex glass containers and these have been used in later experiments. Normally the stress was applied after the reservoir was filled with liquid. The physical aspects of the corrosion have been recorded by time-lapse photography. In order to assess the extent of cracking the negatives were projected onto a screen at a magnification of approximately 10 (the specimen dimensions were used to calibrate this), and the cracks which were above the 2.5mm (on the specimen) threshold counted and measured.

The chemistry of the process has been examined by analysing the corrodent for glass and resin fragments. Initially, atomic absorption spectroscopy was used to determine the inorganic ions (from the glass corrosion) in solution. However this method is rather wasteful of solution and somewhat insensitive so that when aluminium ions were established as the major product we decided to use a spectroscopic method which required a smaller aliquot. The method [9] chosen involves measuring the absorbance at 550nm due to a Xylenol orange-aluminium complex at a pH of 3-4. Calibration curves were obtained from solutions of known pH. Thus hydrochloric acid solutions could be analysed by removing about 0.5 cm³ for buffering and analysis. Since aqueous acetic acid solutions can be buffered to these pH values, a small volume could be removed for analysis by visible spectroscopy and returned subsequently, thereby restricting changes in the volume of the corrodent. Thin layer chromatography has been used to determine any resin fragments.

3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The photographs in Fig. 2 confirm that environmental stress corrosion cracking of glass fibre reinforced unsaturated polyester resin laminates occurs in a relatively short period of time. It is seen that a specimen immersed in 2M hydrochloric acid in the absence of any stress is not prone to cracking. Even over longer periods no crack formation has been observed. Similarly under an applied stress in the absence of the corrodent, only a few edge cracks are formed and these do not grow to any significant length. Over longer periods there is no noticeable crack propagation. However, the synergism between the acid and stress is seen by the formation of a large number of edge cracks within a few hours of immersing a stressed sample in 2M HCl (Fig.2).

3.1 Physical Aspects of Corrosion

Fig. 3 shows typical photographs of a specimen corroded in 2M aqueous hydrochloric acid initially, after 0 hours and after 800 hours. A number of phenomena are observed. Firstly, edge cracks are formed which grow slowly into the transverse ply. Secondly, some edge cracks run completely across the specimen to form transverse cracks. Thirdly, these cracks do not produce strong enough noise signals for acoustic emission studies and have a characteristically diffuse appearance in contrast to those formed in a normal tensile test. Fourthly, after a longer time a large number of edge cracks of a diffuse "furry" nature are formed.

In order to correlate the failure behaviour with the chemistry of the corrosion it is necessary to define a suitable parameter which is a measure of the observed cracking phenomenon.

This is a rather complex problem so that we have recorded the lengths and numbers of edge cracks above a measurable threshold of 2.5mm. This exercise is further complicated by the formation of the very small "furry" cracks which develop at later stages of the process as shown in Fig. 3b.

Fig. 4 shows a series of crack distribution curves at 12 minute intervals throughout the stress corrosion of a coupon specimen in 2M aqueous hydrochloric acid with an applied stress of $0.8 \sigma_{tlu}$.

Fig. 2 : Corrosion Cracking of Polyester GRP under various conditions:

- | | | | | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|---------------------------------------|-----------|---|--|
| (a) | (b) | (c) | (d) | (e) | (f) |
| 2M HCl, $\sigma_a = 0$,
3 hours | 2M HCl, $\sigma_a = 0.8 \sigma_{tlu}$
2 hours | Air,
$0.8 \sigma_{tlu}$
3 hours | 150 hours | distilled water
$0.82 \sigma_{tlu}$,
3 hours | Aqueous
acetic acid,
$0.7 \sigma_{tlu}$,
3 hours |

- | | |
|---------|-----------|
| (a) | (b) |
| 0 hours | 800 hours |

Fig. 3 : Corrosion Cracking of Polyester GRP in 2M HCl with $\sigma_a = 0.8 \sigma_{tlu}$ after

Fig. 4 The crack distribution curves for a specimen corroded in 2M HCl with the applied stress $\sigma_a = 0.8\sigma_{tu}$, l = crack length. The serial number refers to a list of cracks in ascending length. The vertical lines represent the number of cracks traversing the specimen.

Each curve has been obtained by plotting the serial numbers of the cracks arranged in order of increasing length. A small number of edge cracks are seen to be present initially and are formed immediately on application of the stress in the presence of the aqueous acid. Fewer initial cracks are observed in laminates post-cured at lower temperatures during which lower thermal stresses arise. It seems probable therefore that these cracks originate at defects resulting from damage caused by specimen preparation. As shown above, control experiments show that these cracks do not grow in the absence of a corrodent or in a corrodent in the absence of a stress. After an induction period more edge cracks are formed in the transverse ply and after 36 minutes 80% are less than 6mm long and 6% have formed complete transverse cracks. After 168 minutes 63% are less than 6mm long and 10% of the cracks run completely across the transverse ply. The steep initial

gradient to these curves is because crack initiation is rapid compared to crack growth. The implication of the shallow gradient, to the curves at longer lengths is that these small cracks have a low growth rate and since the gradients do not appear to diverge with time, the rate of growth would appear to be independent of crack length.

The subsequent formation of diffuse 'furry' cracks which creep into the specimen is further confirmation that crack initiation is rapid. Eventually these grow larger than 2.5mm and obscure the counting procedure so that after about 3 hours in 2M hydrochloric acid and depending on the applied stress, the differentiation between cracks at the threshold becomes impracticable and consequently we have no meaningful data after this stage. It is also apparent from Fig. 4 that the cracks seem to be formed in bursts; crack initiation inhibited while the new ones grow. Therefore, in order to assess this corrosion we have chosen to plot the cumulative crack number n and cumulative crack length l_m . The results are presented in Fig. 5. As can be seen from the graphs, the general trend outlined above is the continuous production of small cracks. In Fig. 5 it is seen that the cumulative crack length and crack number curves have similar trends but the average crack length is larger at higher applied stresses (5.9 mm at $\sigma_a = 0.8 \sigma_{tlu}$; 3.8 mm at $0.39 \sigma_{tlu}$). At intermediate stresses the trends are also intermediate.

Fig. 5 The rate of formation and growth of cracks in the transverse ply of a 0°/90°/0° laminate immersed in 2M aqueous hydrochloric acid at two different applied stresses. $\sigma_a = 0.8 \sigma_{tlu}$ ■ total crack number ● cumulative crack length (l_T). □, ○, $\sigma_a = 0.39 \sigma_{tlu}$

Furthermore, it can be seen that the average crack length apparently does not change with time; it is clear therefore that small cracks grow faster than large ones and that after the initial burst of corrosion cracking the cumulative crack length/time curve becomes reasonably linear.

$$\text{Thus } l_T = kt \quad \dots (1)$$

where l_T is the cumulative crack length at time t and k is the rate constant.

Since the average crack length \bar{l} is constant

$$l_T = n\bar{l} \quad \dots (2)$$

where n is the total number of cracks at time t

$$\text{Therefore } \frac{dl_T}{dt} = \bar{l} \frac{dn}{dt} \quad \dots (3)$$

Therefore it would appear that cracks are nucleated at a constant rate.

On this interpretation the rate of crack initiation (dn/dt), measured by the slope of the latter part of the curves in Fig. 5, is higher at higher applied stresses and in Fig. 6 it is seen that a reasonably linear relationship between dl_T/dt ($\propto dn/dt$) and the applied stress, σ_a exists. This can be represented by the equation

$$\frac{dl_T}{dt} = k\sigma_a + \text{constant} \quad \dots (4)$$

Fig. 6 The relationship between the applied stress (σ_a) and the limiting rate of change of cumulative crack length (dl_T/dt).

The implications of this relationship need further study; however since increasing σ_a can mean a larger crack opening displacement then it is possible that a larger surface area for chemical attack will have been exposed. It must be understood however, that an alternative view could be that stress enhances chemical corrosion at local defect sites. Furthermore a strain threshold exists below which stress corrosion does not occur.

Since \bar{l} is apparently constant so that the larger cracks are growing more slowly than the smaller ones, it would appear that chemical corrosion rather than large differences in apparent stress, is rate determining. To a first approximation the high population of cracks means that stress concentrations at crack tips are comparatively small for all sizes of crack.

Therefore, it would seem reasonable to suggest that crack propagation is controlled by the rates of diffusion of reactants and products along them; thus the large ones grow more slowly.

Fig. 7 Effect of aqueous solutions on edge cracking at similar σ . ■ (Crack number), ● (○) 2M HCl $0.8\sigma_{TLU}$, ■, ● 0.1M HCl (buffered with CH_3COONa to pH 3.8), $0.7\sigma_{TLU}$, □, ○ distilled water, $0.82\sigma_{TLU}$. In air $0.8\sigma_{TLU}$ no cracks grew above 2.5 mm threshold.

Fig. 7 shows that at similar applied stresses the rate of corrosion is dependent on the nature of the acid, thereby confirming that stress corrosion cracking is a real affect. In air, no cracks grew above the threshold even after seven days, whereas significant corrosion in the form of edge cracks was noticeable after only a few hours in acidic environments. The average length of these corrosion cracks is larger in the presence of acids ($\bar{l} = 5.8$ mm) than in distilled water ($\bar{l} = 3.8$ mm) and air $\bar{l} \ll 2.5$ mm. The finite degree of corrosion in the presence of distilled water is probably due to the slight acidity of the distilled water which had a pH of 5. The rate of corrosion as defined by the limiting slope $d\bar{l}_T/dt$ is seen to be larger in stronger acids. Although only a limited number of results are available at present Fig. 8 shows that the rate appears to be a function of the acidity of the solution.

Fig. 8 Effect of pH on crack nucleation (dl_{cr}/dt) $\sigma_a=0.7-0.8\sigma_{tlu}$

Fig. 9 The concentration of metal ions appearing during immersion in 20 cm² of 3M H₂SO₄ under a tensile stress of 0.5 σ_{tlu} laminate surface area in contact with the solution is 32.4 cm². The mole fractions in the glass are $x_{Al}(\text{glass})=0.18$, $x_{Ca}(\text{glass})=0.21$, $x_{Na}(\text{glass})=0.006$.

To assess the chemistry involved in this phenomenon we have analysed the corroded for glass fragments and resin fragments. The results of an analysis of the laminate surfaces have not proved significant but this may be because the cracks are growing in the inner layer. Fig. 9 gives the analysis by atomic absorption spectroscopy for a laminate stressed in aqueous 3M sulphuric acid at 50% of the first transverse cracking stress, σ_{tlu} . It is clear that glass fibre corrosion occurs and that aluminium ions appear more rapidly than calcium ions even though the mole fraction of calcium in the glass is higher. However, analysis of the glass fibres by electron probe showed a core structure with the outer sheaf depleted of all ions. Also, calcium rich deposits have been detected in laminates and on 'burnt-off-fibres'. Therefore calcium ions are trapped in the matrix. Since the solubilities of aluminium and calcium salts are similar and would be expected to be in solution at these low levels then either the concentrations at the crack tips are such that the slight differences cause precipitation of calcium salts or that a calcium polyester soap can be formed.

Silicon is not detectable in the corroded. On the other hand, maleic acid is detectable in small quantities which suggests that specific parts of the polyester molecule are susceptible to hydrolysis. This is to be expected since hydrolysed fumarate links would remain attached to the styrene bridges, whereas any maleate links which are less reactive to a growing polystyryl radical and are more likely to remain isolated and hence extractable after hydrolysis.

Since aluminium ions would appear to be the main product of glass corrosion in aqueous sulphuric acid environments we have, in the following experiments, only analysed for aluminium. This simplifies the technique and in particular aqueous acetic acid buffered with sodium acetate and containing the xylenol orange, as a complexing agent, has enabled samples of the solution to be removed for short periods, for analysis by visible spectroscopy, and then returned. Fig. 10 shows the simultaneous accumulation of aluminium ions in the corroded as corrosion cracking occurs. Fig. 11 is a plot of the extent of cracking (defined by l_{cr}) against the concentration of aluminium in the corroded for two different experiments. It is reasonably linear within the experimental errors involved in crack measurement and the detection of aluminium ions. Since the line passes through the origin we conclude that when

Fig. 10 The Relationship between stress cracking of the transverse ply and the corrosion of glass fibres as shown by the accumulation of aluminium ions in aqueous acetic acid buffered to 3.8. $\sigma_a = 0.7\sigma_{tfa}$ ● crack formation ○ $[Al^{2+}]$.

Fig. 11 The effect of transverse damage on the accumulated aluminium ion concentration in aqueous acetic acid solutions: $\sigma_a = 0.7\sigma_{tfa}$ ● CH_3COOH/CH_3COONa pH=3.8; ○ CH_3COOH/CH_3COONa pH=3.2; ⊙ extrapolated from ○.

no cracks are present, aluminium ions cannot be leached out of the laminate: Experiments in which 0° faces only were in contact with the acid, much less Al^{3+} is extracted. Thus it would appear that glass corrosion is a result of stress corrosion edge cracking and that the interface between the glass and resin acts as a pathway through which the attack can proceed. Certainly the glass fibres are seen to be corroded when examined in the microscope, and to exhibit the characteristic spiral cracks and a core structure similar to those in Fig. 13 which we [1] have already reported. These results are in support of those presented in Fig. 7 since the rate of glass corrosion would be expected to be higher in the presence of a mineral acid than in an organic acid.

What is not yet clear is the nature of the interface bond. Certainly, the 'furry' cracks described above suggest that the interface bond may not be satisfactory. In order to establish the effect of the interface bond we have examined [10] an anhydride cured epoxy resin (Epikote 828) laminate in which ester groups are also present and for which previous studies [8] have shown that resin-fibre debonds can be controlled. Thus stress corrosion ought to be possible above the whitening stress but not below it. However, stress corrosion cracking is possible at strains lower than that for debonding, as shown in Fig. 12. In contrast to the polyesters, the edge cracks are less in number, do not have the same diffuse character and the 'furry' cracks do not appear. Epoxy laminates would appear, therefore, to be less prone to wicking along the interface.

69 hours 164.5 hours 165 hours

Fig. 12 : Environmental Stress Cracking of $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$
Epoxy/Glass fibre laminate in 0.5M aqueous
sulphuric acid $\sigma_a = 0.3 \sigma_{tlu}$

Fig. 13: Glass Fibres after 4 days in
0.5M Aqueous Sulphuric Acid.

More surprisingly after about 7-14 days a crack propagates rapidly through all three plies (normally outside the liquor) to cause a clean brittle fracture, with splitting in the outer plies. The polyester coupons do not fail in this manner, therefore the mechanisms of stress corrosion differ for these two matrices. Since both resin and glass degradation may be occurring, we are examining model composites in which the glass fibres are completely encased in resin, so that attack on or diffusion through the resin will be necessary prior to corrosion.

CONCLUSIONS

The application of stress to glass reinforced polyesters in aqueous acidic environments leads to the rapid degradation of the transverse ply in $0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$ laminates. The use of cut coupon specimens has enabled the corrosion cracking to be related to the chemistry of the degradation process. The nature of the phenomenon is such that exposed edges enable glass corrosion and transverse cracking to occur rapidly. The cracks grow in from the edges and in the limit are controlled by diffusion of the environment to the crack tip so that the long cracks grow more slowly than the small ones.

It is therefore absolutely necessary that glass fibres, whether at cut edges or due to laminate defects, should not be exposed to acidic environments. Stress and the environment are synergistic so that laminates need to be prepared without large inherent strains. In particular it should be noted that excessive thermal strains can be readily built into these plies, by post heating, because of differences between the expansion coefficients of the resin and glass fibres.

The phenomena reported here need further study and experiments in which the edges are carefully sealed are underway.

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